

than other pests because once the damage is apparent, it is essentially too late to effectively control the pest; thus, farmers and researchers may be tempted to use prophylactic applications for "safety." Infestations of stem borer during the 1996 dry season were

the highest seen for many years (infestation varied from a 0 to 8% proportion of total panicles infested). Although the damage looked spectacular, it has been repeatedly shown that damage at low to moderate

yield levels has little to no effect on crop yield. Data presently being collected also suggest that plants retain sufficient yield component plasticity even at higher yield levels (>8 t ha⁻¹) to compensate for damaged panicles. ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Butachlor safener combinations for weed control in direct-seeded puddled rice

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Weed competition is a major constraint to the productivity of broadcast-seeded rice. Although manual weeding controls weeds effectively, because of the absence of rows, it is difficult, time-consuming, and costly. In addition, labor is scarce. Butachlor, the recommended herbicide, controls weeds effectively, but is toxic to germinating rice seedlings. The use of a safener, an antidote, protects rice seedlings from butachlor injury effectively without any adverse effect on weed control.

A field experiment was conducted during the 1994 and 1995 wet seasons at HPKV, Palampur (32° 6' N, 76° 3' E,

1,290 m altitude). The soil of the test site was silty clay loam, with pH 6.9, 1.2% organic C, 364 kg available N ha⁻¹, 21 kg available P ha⁻¹, and 326 kg available K ha⁻¹. Sprouted seeds of variety HPU2216 were sown at 100 kg ha⁻¹ by the broadcast method onto puddled soil on 19 Jun 1994 and 26 Jun 1995. The treatments (see table) were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications. The data analyzed by standard analysis of variance and treatment means were compared with the LSD test at the 5% level.

Weed samples were taken from a 25 cm × 25 cm area and oven-dried at 70 °C, and dry weight was recorded. Grain yield was recorded from a 7.5-m² net plot area. Plant samples from a 0.5-m² area were taken at harvest to record yield components. The emergence count was recorded from a 0.5-m² area at 18 d after sowing (DAS). The dominant weeds were *Echinochloa crus-galli*,

E. colona, *Ammania baccifera*, *Scirpus* sp., *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *C. esculentus*, *Aeschynomene indica*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Commelina forskalli*.

Butachlor without safener applied at 2 or 7 DAS caused toxicity to rice seedlings, but this was significantly less when applied at 7 DAS than at 2 DAS. Other butachlor safener combinations also caused acute toxicity symptoms, but rice plants were able to recover. Butachlor at 2 kg ha⁻¹ + safener at 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ (7 DAS) was the most effective combination for yield and weed control. Rice yield of the butachlor at 1.5 kg ha⁻¹ + safener at 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ (2 and 7 DAS) treatments was equal to that of the crop that received two hand weedings. At each time of application (i.e., 2 or 7 DAS), butachlor with safener at 0.094 or 0.188 kg ha⁻¹ controlled weeds effectively and increased rice grain yield significantly over its application without safener (see table). ■

Effect of butachlor safener combinations on emergence count, panicles m², panicle weight, grain yield, and weed dry weight in direct-seeded puddled rice.

Treatment	Time of application (DAS) ^a	Rate (kg ai ha ⁻¹)	Emergence count (g m ⁻²)		Panicles (no. m ⁻²)		Panicle weight (g)		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)	
			1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994	1995	1994 ^b	1995
			Butachlor ^c	2	1.5	199	148	324	168	1.53	1.58	3.4
Butachlor + safener ^d	2	1.5 + 0.094	292	239	420	234	1.68	1.75	4.5	2.7	3.24 (10.1)	77
Butachlor + safener	2	1.5 + 0.188	316	265	467	248	1.75	1.81	5.0	3.0	2.41 (6.8)	43
Butachlor	7	1.5	257	195	373	195	1.55	1.61	4.0	2.0	4.76 (25.5)	81
Butachlor + safener	7	1.5 + 0.094	323	261	427	242	1.71	1.77	4.5	3.0	3.93 (15.1)	47
Butachlor + safener	7	1.5 + 0.188	342	281	463	261	1.77	1.88	4.9	3.2	3.37 (11.0)	31
Safener	2	0.188	368	324	327	188	1.35	1.40	3.4	1.2	8.97 (80.2)	399
Butachlor + safener	7	2.0 + 0.188	338	272	492	295	1.79	1.92	5.2	3.7	1.10 (0.8)	12
Hand weeding twice	25 & 45	–	365	324	472	264	1.83	1.95	5.0	3.3	3.63 (12.7)	27
Unweeded check	–	–	361	329	296	184	1.32	1.39	3.0	1.2	9.58 (91.7)	406
LSD (0.05)			25	40	59	40	0.17	0.20	0.6	0.6	1.15	21

^aDays after sowing. ^bData transformed to $\sqrt{x + 0.5}$ transformation. Values in parentheses are the means of original values. ^cFormulation: Trapp 50 EC. ^dTrade name S901A, chemical name 4,6 dichloro-2-phenyl pyrimidine.